

A CAD-based Approach for the Kinematic and Position Analysis of Planar Mechanisms

Giovanni Berselli^{a,b}, Federico Balugani^c

(a) Dept. of Mech., Energy, Management and Trans. Eng., University of Genova, Genova, Italy

(b) Advanced Robotics Dept. (ADVR), Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT), Genova, Italy

(c) Borghi S.p.a., Castelfranco Emilia (MO), Italy

giovanni.berselli@unige.it, federico.balugani@borghi.it,

Abstract—Planar mechanisms are widely employed in automated machinery in order to perform various tasks. The finished product is typically obtained through a sequence of operations performed by a multi-actuator architecture, where each task is accomplished by a dedicated mechanism driven by a position-controlled electric motor. In this context, the purpose of the present abstract, is to introduce an approach for the kinematic analysis of planar mechanism using a parametric sketch. The approach is conceived thinking of mechanical designers who usually work with 2D or 3D parametric CAD without the aid of symbolic algebra tool (e.g., Maple or Matlab) or advanced CAE suite.

Index Terms— Position Analysis, Planar Mechanisms, CAD Tools, Servo-Mechanisms

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, a typical automated machinery comprises several position-controlled motors, where each motor typically controls a one degree of freedom mechanism (1 d.o.f.). When high-speed linear motion is required, the designer usually chooses to employ a slider crank mechanism [1]. On the other hand, when oscillatory motion is required a four-bar mechanism can be adopted. The two above mentioned mechanisms are widely used and can be easily synthesized in order to perform simple tasks with the aid of a CAD software. Sometimes the mechanical designer has to deal with more complex planar linkages such as mechanisms with more than four links (For Example Fig. 1) or four-bar mechanisms with particular connecting rod motion (e.g., the Roberts straight line

Fig. 1. An Example of a six links mechanism

linkage) [2]. In these cases, the synthesis problem becomes more intricate and can be approached using various methods, including the precision points graphical approach, synthesis through optimization or synthesis through repeated position analyses [3]. Having the mechanical designer in mind, three main approaches can be listed in order to address the problem of kinematic analysis of 1 d.o.f. mechanisms:

- *Mathematical approach*, which requires the mathematical model of the linkage. This can be generally found writing the closure equations of the linkage and finding a solution that can be in closed form or obtained with a numerical algorithm [4]. The main drawback of this approach is that reversing mechanism input and output variables is not so quick and requires an additional mathematical effort.
- *CAD/CAE approach*, which requires a simulation environment for rigid body kinematic analysis [5]. The user has to develop a 3D model with constraints in order to describe the behavior of the mechanism in the simulation environment. Once the mechanism is correctly constrained a driving link can be defined in order to simulate the mechanism through different configurations solving the kinematic analysis.
- *2D Parametric Sketcher approach*, using a software with embedded constraint solver [6]. The mechanism can be drawn as a sketch inserting geometric constraints and relevant user-defined parameters (such as the length of the links). The sketch needs to be fully constrained selecting a “driving dimension” which works as input variable. The embedded constraint solver will solve the position analysis whenever the input value is updated.

Fig. 2. Robert Straight line linkage.

Fig. 3. Tools integration and optimization loop.

The latter approach is the most commonly employed by mechanical designers due to its simplicity and quickness. Unfortunately, only static pictures of the mechanism position and velocities can be retrieved. The aim of the present abstract is to present an example developed with Autodesk Inventor which is the CAD used by *Borghi S.p.a.* (www.borghi.com) and provide some insights to perform a complete position analysis through a sequence of different input values.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE APPROACH

A well-known mechanism is chosen for the discussion, the Roberts straight line linkage, shown in Fig. 2: the mechanism is a four bar, whose geometry requires that links 2 and 3 and segments BP and CP on coupler link 4 have the same length, while the length of frame link 1 is twice the length of the segment BC on link 4. To develop the mechanism model, a reference frame is positioned as in Fig. 2a, with its origin O coinciding with coupler point P when the mechanism is in its symmetric position. When the mechanism is moved in both directions from its reference symmetric configuration of Fig. 2a, the coupler point P traces a trajectory that for a certain motion range is very close to a straight-line coinciding with the x axis (Fig. 2b). A typical problem is to determine the trajectory (x_p, y_p) of point P and to determine the angular velocities of the links and the velocity components of point P , this problem is well addressed in [2]. In order to create the model of the chosen mechanism within Inventor, a rough sketch is first created, then dimensional and geometric constraint are added, then θ_2 is chosen as “driving dimension”, and finally some driven dimensions are added. The first driven dimension is the distance between A and P along the x axis and the second is the distance, along y , between a fixed line positioned under the frame link and the point P . These two driven dimensions are used to calculate x_p and y_p as differences, thus accounting for their respective signs. With reference to Fig. 3, $l_2 = l_3 = BP = CP = 180$ mm, $BC = 120$ mm and $AD = 240$ mm, have been considered. Using iLogic, a tool provided with Autodesk Inventor, it is possible to enhance the process by:

- Creating a User Interface (U.I.) panel to modify specific parameters.
- Embedding Excel files within the CAD file.
- Implementing rules, written in VB.NET.

In Fig. 2 a simple U.I. panel with a slider has been created in order to vary the value of θ_2 from 53 deg to 87 deg with step 1 deg. The user can move the slider step by step and the sketch automatically updates the dimensions while a simple rule writes the values of x_p and y_p inside consecutive Excel rows. Once the entire sequence of input values has been swept, the Excel file will contain the values to create the position analysis plot.

III. CONCLUSIONS

A practical approach for solving the kinematic analysis of planar mechanisms has been presented. The mentioned procedure is quick to be implemented and can be used iteratively during the design stages by mechanical designers without particular expertise in mathematics or CAE software.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Pellicciari, G. Berselli, and F. Balugani, “On designing optimal trajectories for servo-actuated mechanisms: Detailed virtual prototyping and experimental evaluation,” *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 2039–2052, 2015.
- [2] P. Fanghella, G. Berselli, and L. Bruzzone, “Analytical or Computer-Aided Graphical Methods for Introductory Teaching of Mechanism Kinematics?” in *New Trends in Educational Activity in the Field of Mechanism and Machine Theory*, ser. Mechanisms and Machine Science, J. García-Prada and C. Castejón, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 149–156.
- [3] P. Magnani and L. Ruggieri, *Meccanismi Per Macchine Automatiche*. Hoepli, 1986.
- [4] M. Callegari, P. Fanghella, and F. Pellicano, *Meccanica applicata alle macchine*. UTET Università, 2017.
- [5] J. L. S. Martínez and J. Carballeira, “Enhancing Mechanism and Machine Science Learning by Creating Virtual Labs with ADAMS,” in *New Trends in Educational Activity in the Field of Mechanism and Machine Theory*, ser. Mechanisms and Machine Science, J. C. García-Prada and C. Castejón, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2014, pp. 221–228.
- [6] B. Bettig and C. M. Hoffmann, “Geometric Constraint Solving in Parametric Computer-Aided Design,” *Journal of Computing and Information Science in Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 021001, 2011.